

Love in the Time of Cholera Portrays the Love in Different Shades at Different Stages of Life

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ABSTRACT:

Gabriel Garcia Marquez is a well known writer of Latin America, who elevated Magic-realism through his works. Gabriel Garcia Marquez is one among the Big Four, who is closely associated with. *Love in the Time of Cholera* is one of the novels but a romantic novel. This novel gives a different definition for love which is elevated. The love varies at different stages and ages. The narrator also represents different shades of love which has been described in this novel. This paper discusses the love in different perspective through different shades at different stages of life.

Key words: epistolary love, platonic love, interracial love, masochistic love, etc. were discussed in this paper.

20th century Colombian writer, who represented the Third World reality through his works, known affectionately as *Gabo* throughout Latin America is Gabriel Jose de la Concordia Garcia Marquez / Gabriel Garcia Marquez (in Spanish naming customs: the first is paternal family name: Gabriel and the second is maternal family name: Marquez) is a novelist, short- story writer, screenwriter and journalist. He won Nobel Prize for Literature in 1982 for *One Hundred Years of Solitude*. His works are notable for employing narrative style of Magical Realism. Literary movement of 1960's and 1970's was known as Latin American Boom; Gabriel Garcia Marquez is one among the Big Four, who is closely associated with. Gabriel Garcia Marquez is regarded as "He gave us our History" by Isabel Allende. He made attention towards Colombia's history which acclaimed world widely through *One Hundred Years of Solitude*. He became worldly acclaimed writer through this novel.

Among his novels, *Love in the Time of Cholera* is different to remaining novels. It is a romantic novel which remains different from his writings. The novels have mark of themes of political, history and solitude in remaining novels. In each of his novel we can see the elements of love and sex but the narrator mainly focussed this particular novel to focus on them with different shades of love and there draw backs with which the characters suffer with. He presents the love as painful as many writers focussed in their writings but in this novel we can evident the gain of love and shows the path of long waiting and the love can be gained in this life itself unless the waiting is meaningful. In fact, they too evident in the *Love in the Time of Cholera* but dominant theme is love at different ages.

Love in the Time of Cholera is a novel which portrays the themes of love, passion, Gerontophobia, history, feminism, solitude, class division etc,. We can evident the biographical element of Marquez's father, Gabriel Eligio Garcia and mother, Lusia Santiago Marquez 's love story in the character's of Florentino Ariza and Fermina Daza. But his parent's love is success but the love of the characters in the novel is successful at the old age which costs their life. As the mother Fermina realizes that the hasty love results in difficulties is the experience of the narrator's mother's experience about her love.

The title *Love in the Time of Cholera* represents in Spanish 'Colera' as human rage or ire or passion. Garcia Marquez portrays love in the novel as love between old people, love between adolescents, love between an old man and a young virgin, love with prostitutes, love as infidelity, epistolary love, platonic love, interracial love, masochistic love, etc,. Marquez also represents "love as illness". He also presents love is possible at different stage of life, like in youth and old age, Platonic and erotic, lawful and unlawful, ephemeral and eternal, childlike yet sublime. The lover waiting for reply is like 'devastation of Cholera.' (61)

The novel gives its own meaning and definition of love at different stages. Through the characters, he displays love as sometimes 'ideal' and sometimes as 'deprave'. The love also

changes its form in course of time. The narrator also presents displayed all possible stages of love - at twenty, at forty, at fifty or at eighty. These are the crucial stages of the life to experience of love. Through the presentation, it is convinced that Garcia Marquez has sounded the depths of the human heart.

Though the novel is “good old fashioned love story” with its “intentional return to nineteenth-century realism” (191) as Bell-Villada said but Marquez shows the love in a different perspective is discussed in the following discussion. The presentation of love by Marquez is identified as ‘nymphomaniac of the heart’ in an interview for Playboy magazine (February 1983, p. 178)

In one the essay by Roberto González-Echevarría, they call the affairs in the novel as ‘crepuscular affair’. Every round character have an affair but the reason behind their affairs are explained in further study.

Adolescent love:

Through Florentino Ariza and Fermina Daza, Marquez portrays adolescent love. At the age of youth, Florentino Ariza falls in love with a twelve years old girl, Fermina Daza. The love starts with letters as he works in telegraph office which he describes as people think “Telegraph had something magical about it” (57). As the letters will exchange the love between the lovers but in his case the love starts with a letter. He saw for first time when he goes to deliver the letter in her house, there he comes across Fermina Daza. At youth, the sign language is the communication and the exchanges of letters are the expressions. The loves have no difference of class but later it becomes the hurdle in the life of Florentino. They never exchange of words but sign language is the expression. The waiting for the lover is the pain which Florentino undergoes and he enjoys the pain. When he suffers with cholera it is not the medical illness rather psychological illness. Fermina Daza is an intelligent girl who never shows the love at the age of youth but she too undergoes the illness when she subject to house arrest as everyone thought as Cholera. As she suffers and exiles from him, her love increases through letters before she reaches the place.

Undoubtedly, Florentino Ariza is a passionate lover as he hides the things of her lover as token of love. As he is totally driven way by the currents of love, from which he cannot come out of it.

Aunt Escolastica warns that it is very difficult to predict the true nature of man. But the infatuation which Fermina has created on Florentino does not create any doubt. But, she places herself in a state of confusion whether to accept his love or not. She prays to God to come true of her aunt's predictions. It clearly states that the adolescent state of mind in which she is placed in but Florentino have a clear picture of his love which he expects the love from her. She suffers to see him when he is not in her sight. Adolescent love is a secret love which has fear in love as well due to insecure. The imagination during the adolescent age is magnificent and delightful of their lovers.

Fermina feels that he is a man who comes from heaven without a woman and realizes that he too needs love like her. The important quality of love which Florentino wants to keep is his virginity for the sake of Fermina, as he believes that losing virginity is betraying his true love. He tends in to the madness of love that he eats the gardenias which she grows so as to taste her taste.

In the case of Fermina Daza, the separation from him makes her to realize of her love as infatuation. He slowly gets forgets of him. But the delirium of Florentino Ariza increases due to the separation. Though he writes letters which reaches the places before her but it cannot sustain longer. In the case of Hildebrand Sanchez, who is two years younger than Fermina, who falls in love with a married man. He is twenty years older than her who displays that love has no age to fall in or experience or no age criteria. It is one of the examples that Marquez gives which displays love happens in all possible stages.

Parental love:

Parental love which has no boundaries. Lorenzo Daza, Fermina Daza's father, have so many plans to settle her life in a wonderful way and married to a well settled family. He is married to a good family through which he gets social status in the society. But he migrates from San Juan de la Cienega to hide his background by selling his properties to the colonial city with dreams. But one

day, he faces an unimaginable situation that a man comes to marry his daughter who belongs to lower class. Then he warns him and takes her daughter to his relatives' houses to change her mind. In a due course of time, she forgets him as she realizes that as immature and infatuation. Through his daughter's change of mind, he is successful in his deeds.

Lorenzo Daza gives her daughter his dream life through fixing match with Dr. Juvenal Urbino. He justifies his deeds as parental love. While, Florentino Ariza's mother, Transisto Ariza gives her full support to her son in realizing his dream come true i.e., the love with Fermina Daza. Transisto as a mother, she worries only about his situation which his love drawn in to. When he suffers with Choleric disease, she understands his situation and tries to console him. She even sends a widower, Nazaret, to his bed, as she misunderstood as his son's love is erotic love. Later, she felts his son to overcome the limerence by putting a damper on his emotional capacity. But she tends to fail as it increases his erotic love. Transisto suffers with dementia due to his son's behaviour. She is drawn to a situation as she asks every lady who comes across to marry her son. Transisto felt his son's pain as her's and she strengthens his son's heart to bear the pain and advises to enjoy the prostration. Such is the love and affection of Transisto towards her son. She wants his son to enjoy his love as she missed in her life. The comparison between Lorenzo Daza and Transisto Ariza both have parental love on their daughter and son respectively but Lorenzo is successful to fulfil his dream forcing on her daughter but as a mother, Transisto is remained insane which brought by her son's passionate love.

Ideal vs Depraved Love:

Love sometimes can be 'ideal' and sometimes 'depraved' as in the case of Lorenzo Daza. He comes from a low class family who is a braggart and boor, mule trader marries Fermina who comes from a typical family of the region. But when her daughter wants to marry a man who comes from a low class family, Lorenzo is against to her love. He wants not to happen in her daughter's life. He is intransigence to his opinions. Fermina also blames herself that her love is a hasty decision after marriage as 'not of love but a sacramental cloak some premature mistake' (86)

The point of realization makes love as 'depraved' but for Lorenzo, it is 'ideal' but in the case of her daughter's love is 'depraved'.

For Transisto Ariza love as infidelity which has happened to her. As a result she gave birth to Florentino Ariza. But she never regrets to her situation in which she is drawn. She is faithful to her love that she never reveals that her son's father is Don Pius V Loayza with whom she has occasional alliance. Nevertheless, she hopes her son to receive pragmatic love.

Dr. Juvenal Urbino says that 'no innocence more dangerous than innocence of age' (13) The innocence is the reason why the people fall in love at any age for which Marquez contradicts the views and he gives an example of Jeremiah de Saint at an old age who leads a secret love with a mulatto who is no less than 40 years. As Jeremiah justifies that to experience love requires no age. Though it looks awkward and the society names as an illicit love but the love requires at all ages. The reason what the old age needs is the companion to lead a happy life through fulfilling their wishes that will be experienced only in love. As the death is inevitable, the old age reminds them and decay them. To escape from that nostalgia they need love but not compassion towards them. The author sets an example through Jeremiah de Saint how to lead life in old age. When Dr. Urbino comes to know the truth of Jeremiah's secret of love, he felt betrayed but then he realizes his intention through the words of mulatto. But women think that keeping secret love as 'an atavistic custom of a certain kind of man'

Marquez also predicts that the lover affairs were slow and difficult. They were often disturbed by 'sinister omens' which made their lives endless. The sinister omens are the hurdles which becomes the villains or tragedies in the lives which results in separation.

Racial Love:

Through mulatto, the author represents racial love and represents a black woman of honesty who decides to sell the property which she treats as 'death trap of poor'. She spends her valuable time, caring and affection not for money but for love. She stood as an example for black women

who shows different face of the blacks and contradicts the notions in the society though they were treated as low and meagre. Indeed, they too have heart which needs love. Though Jeremiah never reveals his secret love because she is a mulatto who degrades his value in the society but she never contradicts it. She does not attend the funeral to keep her relation as secret as Jeremiah's lover. It represents the degraded position of the black women. The conversation between mulatto and Dr. Urbino displays of their faithfulness and respect towards the relationship as black and Dr. Urbino changes his opinion on blacks. As Ruben Pelayo presents his opinion about blacks in his essay as:

‘... love between socially and economically displaced blacks, in the same way that the death of Dr. Juvenal Urbino provides the opportunity to talk about love among the ruling class’.(10)

The narrator presents the opinion of illicit love through Dr. Urbino

The love in the longest relationship i.e., married life will sustain till to the end which the author focuses in the novel. The relationship in the marriage is described as:

‘No one ever thought that a marriage rooted in such foundations could have any reason not to be happy’.(19)

Through Jeremiah de Saint and mulatto, the narrator depict the conflict between social life and desire to live according to their willing. As Roberto González-Echevarría mentions that Jeremiah commits suicide who could not contradict with the social conventions.

“Courtly love is, at this level, a critique of all social forms, because all convention or institutionalization obstructs love's ultimate goal, which is to forestall death.” (32)

Epistolary Love:

The language he used in the letter of all kinds of flattery. As it is the age of illusion which love is an fascinating and it sometimes provokes to an extreme of no other life in the longing. This instigates them to communicate in secrecy. The only tool of communication is letters. Marquez has used the poetry and gifts to express the love. During the demented trip of Fermina, Florentino and Fermina communicated through passionate letters.

The letters have significant role in the expression of love between Florentino and Fermina at the time of Youth and Old age. They reduce the gap between them at the time of their separation. In fact, the letter acts as mediator for Florentino to get an opportunity to see her for the first time. Later, there are exchanges of letters to impress her. During her vacation, he sent the messages through letters which reaches before her. The letters from Florentino express the passionate love and his longing to see her. Whenever Fermina let in to indecisive and ambiguous, the letters make her towards Florentino's love. Even her cousin, Hildebranda Sanchez, also impressed by the Florentino's letters which express his pain of separation and yearning. These letters stands for Hildebranda to create impressive impression on Florentino which makes her to instigate Fermina to marry him. Though the composition of poems he feels like 'it was finding oasis.'(75) in the deserted love.

Later Dr. Urbino also writes letters to impress her. He writes almost three letters. The difference of the letters which she gets from Florentino which creates anxiety to open the letters but the Urbino's letters causes to frighten her. Urbino sends letters with anonymously with initials as 'J.U.C'. She left them unopened for several days. Since she opens the letters, she felt psychologically alien to the world. As she search of comfort from the writings. He goes in depth of the meaning to take decision on the person. Though he tries to create the opinion on her about him and to know her before marriage but it fails instead it creates traumatic opinion about him. The narrator creates a dismayed situation to Fermina where the love initiated in the case of Florentino has been rejected but Dr. Urbino's letters created alarming. The narrator explains that deciding the opinion on love through letters is contradictory of reality.

At the time of old age, Florentino gets second opportunity to impress Fermina after the death of Dr. Urbino. He takes the chance through requisition letter as a proposal to her. He writes the letters until she gives the chance to him. Through 132 letters, he tries to impress her again at second stage of his love. He throws her into a critical situation where he tries to show the life after her husband's death through his constant persuasion and by letters. After the death of her

husband's death, he started sending letters to convince her as continue her life not as widow and choose her own path; not to fear the conventions of society, family, etc.,. This time she cannot avoid him instead of accepting him. The reasons which stood as obstacles to reach her were made smoothing at the age of 70's.

Later he made as ritual as part of his route of writing and sending letters in which most of them are blank. He even sent pigeon post too. The lovers sent letters through various means like birds, telegram, post, etc.,. The medium may vary but the love cannot. They use various means to make love to live and communicate as in those days they cannot communicate in public. Here, the narrator mentions the modifications of mail to communicate their lovers to convey message in technological progress.

The letters sometimes recite the poems from Florentino's memory which means he felt the poet's words will impress Fermina. Along with letters, Florentino sends gifts like dried leaves, wings of butterflies, the feathers of magic birds, camellia, etc.,. The length of the letter runs into pages which contains the poems from his memory. He names his love as 'his perfect fidelity and his everlasting love.' (61). The gifts which he sends as token for love as Camellia stands as 'flower of promises' (61) On one of his birthday, she sent 'a square centimetre of St. Peter Clavier's habit' which is expensive to his age. The loves they exchange through gifts are the relics of their passion which symbolizes of their eager and longing to meet.

Choleric Love:

Marquez's novel represents the symptoms of love are the symptoms of Choleric disease with which the characters suffer with. The narrator intentionally tends to confuse the symptoms of the disease with their suffering as it happens coincidentally in which the period he represented them. They undergo the treatment but they could not find the reason behind it. The suggestion of the practitioner to Florentino to 'change the air', though the disease may be air borne but in this case the change of air means change of place which in turn change his mind but it never happens instead it increases his pain. His mother underestimate the disease as it will not sustain for lifelong but

Florentino's suffering will be cured only with Fermina's love. The waiting for reply comes as vomiting:

“But when he began to wait for the answer to his first letter, his anguish was complicated by diarrhea and green vomit, he became disoriented and suffered from sudden fainting spells, ” (61)

The situation is intensified with the waiting and comes out as vomiting. According to medical science, the 'green vomit' represents the bile infection but it makes Florentino to feel freshness in his mood swings which makes his mental relaxation as if it comes out of his mind through vomiting. The symptoms reveal the concrete feeling i.e., an urgency of making love. Because of the love sickness, Florentino tends in to a confusion state which leads to the situation of losing the job.

After Florentino succeeds his platonic love and acceptance of his love, he hoist the yellow flag on board of their ship which indicates the ship is quarantined due to cholera. Though, it clearly indicates that they were not attacked by epidemic disease but by cholera which represents in Spanish '*Colera*' as human rage or ire or passion. The reason behind is to live with her the rest of the life and enjoy the love forever.

Ephemeral love:

The narrator presented the ephemeral loves as a recurring theme in the novel. Ephemeral loves are experienced by the irrespective of the ages. The reason behind their ephemeral loves or hurried loves are the consolation of their hearts which they need at the end of their day. The free life they lead in their own way where they cry out their feelings not of sharing bed but other than. Marquez wants to present the deceased life is relieved through hurried loves. Florentino is also born out of Transisto Ariza and Don Plus V Loayza's hurried love.

Love with prostitutes:

Though the prostitutes love is hurried love but the love which they experience is painful and sexual. The bodies of the prostitutes are the evidences of their past. The narrator gives the life of prostitutes is horrible and give birth to the fatherless children in fact illicit children in the society.

Another description Marquez has given about the night birds i.e., make their children nude along with them as they did not want to be guilty of what their mother's are doing which resembles of Paradise. The Paradise is the place where happiness is the only thing prevails which the narrator compares with whorehouse and the angels are compared with prostitutes who wandered with their children in nude. Here the nudity symbolizes that the guilty has no place and not to make the children guilty of their work. In the same way, the people finds pleasure and console their hearts with the company of them who listens their sorrows and depression. In fact, they even cry out the psychological worries which they shed and come out with light hearted. The prostitutes not only provide sensual but also act as companions of their worries even though they not solve them but they share their pain.

Florentino gives the explanation about his affairs with night birds as they find solace with him. The narrator wants to presents as ephemeral love is not physical but psychological pleasure. For Fermina, Florentino gives the explanation they are physical pleasures but the love which he want from Fermina is psychological pleasure.

Erotic love:

According to Eric L. Reinholtz Eroticism defined in Bloom's How to Write about *Gabriel García Márquez*:

“Eroticism can be defined as the artistic representation of sexual desire. While depictions of sexual intercourse and physical desire can be found throughout the novel, not all of them are erotic in nature”.(218)

In the case of Dr. Urbino, his love towards Fermina is erotic love which he realizes during their honeymoon whereas Florentino's love is a platonic love. He married her out of physical attraction. In erotic love, it may become infidelity as it cannot sustain longer. The narrator gives as an example of Dr. Urbino as his erotic love vanishes at old age and he again falls in love with Barbara Lynch. If his love is platonic he would not fall in love again.

The narrator presents erotic love through the character of Dr. Urbino, who tries to win Fermina heart but after their married life it cannot sustain during the difficult times. They feel to lose their relationship and feels emptiness. At the time of old age, they continue their relationship not out of love but dependence. They not even try to open up their minds with the fear that their relationship will break. The erotic love is temporary whereas the platonic love permanent.

García Márquez portrays the barrenness of bourgeois life, the tedium of social rituals, and the gradual decline of physical strength which results an extramarital affairs. The narrator describes the failure of erotic love in the novel with a magnificent passage describing an argument about whether or not there is soap in the bathroom. The gap and emptiness of relationship between them is explained in it to the readers to assume of the married life whom they believe the most happiest couple in the early life of marriage.

Dr. Urbino and Fermina lead a fifty years of happy married life though they have different tastes, different opinions the foundation of the life is love but they never asked themselves whether they live together on the dependence of love or convenience. In fact they never let the question of confession as they fear it may break their relationship or for society but they are deceiving themselves by compromising. Here Jeremiah de Saint is the successful man who led his life at the fullest according to his wish. But in the case of Urbino and Fermina are deceiving each other without confession. Nevertheless, they know that they are not as before.

The love at the old age will sustain or not, perennial or transient is focussed in the novel. The old age has the problems of gaps in the memory, unequivocal signs, illness due to aging, etc,. The narrator gives the solution for the decline of love in the old age due to aging to regard them as 'senile baby' and outreach of pity. The love is just as another phase at the old age of human beings. He presents through Dr. Urbino and Fermina. Fermina treats Dr. Urbino as 'senile baby' out of his aging deeds. Life will make the people learn in time how to avoid the matrimonial catastrophic than to trivial the everyday miseries. This makes how to lead a happy life without outrage in life

which leads psychological trauma. The fatality of dependence at old age will leads to gap in the communication between them. Lack of communication which becomes the hurdle and it replaces with silence where there is no argument which ultimately leads to trivial game. The trivial games leads to fresh wounds as did not interfere in one another's life.

The narrator clearly presents whether love will decline due to aging. Dr. Urbino falls from the tree and he is about to die then he is unable to express his love to his wife, Fermina though they talk to each other. The confession of love is the only chance which he wants to make before leave his breathe. The same feeling which Fermina have to confess the love towards his husband before he die. Though he and she cannot make it but they realize at the time of his death. Their love can begin to decay due to drudgeries and sameness of the everyday routine but the realisation of no second chance or at the eleventh hour made them to confess the love between them. As Marquez mentions in *One Hundred Years of Solitude* as 'second opportunity on earth', Dr.Urbino felt at the time of his death and Fermina also felt the same feeling to express his love which will have second opportunity for them.

Platonic Love:

Florentino's love is Platonic love who has waited for his lover, Fermina for fifty-one years, nine months and four days to hold back her. Though his adolescent love is rejected by his lover Fermina as immature love or infatuation, his awaiting and the days of count will prove that his love is Platonic love. In fact, his rejection made him to realize that a 'man of substance'. Mean while, he realized that money and status are the essential qualities for his love so he run after tirelessly to earn money for that he planned to haul out the treasure from a sunken ship without knowing the place but failed. But he continues his job working tirelessly to achieve higher positions and becomes owner to the ship. Meanwhile he encounters Fermina while she was pregnant, later at poetry competition, at theatre, etc,. Though he notices that Fermina is happy with her husband and children, but he never gave up his hope of reunion with her. He never been pessimistic rather optimistic that one day she would accept him.

Though Florentino has 622 affairs, he never gave up his thinking to Fermina. In fact, Fermina's doubt of not having a woman of his own is cleared with a statement that Florentino gave was "I've remained a virgin for you" (339). Septuagenarian love does not need the bodily pleasure as the body is shrunken due to aging. They waited for 'second chance on earth' which came true after long waiting i.e., fifty-one years, nine months and four days. As Marquez said in *One Hundred Years of Solitude*, as 'did not have second opportunity on earth' but in *Love in the Time of Cholera*, Florentino and Fermina got their second chance on earth after Fermina 's husband's death though Fermina never expects that Florentino wait for such long period. Initially, she felt to accept Florentino's love after her husband's death not even a week passed, Florentino came with a proposal which thrown her in a situation of dubious.

"It is as if García Márquez's faith in and hope for a "minor utopia" and "second chance on earth," however liberating, must always remain clouded by the ominous threat of self-destruction: after all, if the earth itself (evidenced at the novel's close by the setting of deforestation on the Magdalena River) can be permanently destroyed, what is to stop human emotionality, with the death of the body, from succumbing possibly to a similar fate? (77) (DAV I D BUEHRER "A Second Chance on Earth": *The Postmodern and the Post-apocalyptic in García Márquez's Love in the Time of Cholera*)

When she was in dilemma to take decision after she became widow, Florentino is capable of persuading Fermina whenever she is in ambiguous situation through his explanations and sending letters constantly. His platonic love made her to overcome the fear of social constraints and rejection by her children and accept his love. Fermina decides to accept his platonic love. As Roberto González-Echevarría describes that the men and women has freedom to choose their own path irrespective of their age which Fermina and Florentino has been chosen at the age of 70's.

"García Márquez has found, instead, that old age is a more radical vantage point, one from which all of life, all the constraints of life, appear whole, complete, and discardable; a point from

which, freed from anxieties for the future, men and women can pursue whatever interests them most.” (35) (Roberto González-Echevarría, *Love in the Golden Years*)

Florentino’s platonic love is shown through their voyage in a boat which is named: *Nueva Fidelidad*, the name denotes allegorical meaning of their voyage which means “New Fidelity”. The readers were misled as Florentino is projected as sensual lover as he has 622 affairs but at the end of the novel we come to know that he never loves her body but her company which he expresses when Fermina was shy to show her aging body. Florentino celebrates his love by hoisting yellow flag which symbolizes the disease which they suffer though it may not be pandemic but by platonic love.

Marital love:

Fermina Ariza and Juvenal Urbino stands for marital love. Juvenal loves her at first sight, later she convinces herself and marries him. Though their marriage happened due to different reasons but they lived happily after. They gave birth to two children. Their love made that she was the luckiest on earth to have such a husband. Marquez portrays the magic of love in marriage as she modifies herself according to their status and even she bears the insults in mother-in-law’s house. Juvenal Urbino is a faithful and supportive husband to her.

When Fermina comes to know about his illegal relationship with Miss Barbara Lynch, at first she cannot take it easily and felt that his vows which made to her were broken but she forgives him due to the bonding and love towards him and gives a second chance to him. This happens only in marriage which the magical love makes her to forgive him. But due to the aging, they felt alien and detached to each other. They are not even respecting each other and rising of gap between them and even they go to an extent of blaming each other. The reason behind it is silence and not sharing their feelings and emotions. The aging plays an important role to continue their relationship. Both knew that they are continuing their relationship due to ‘dependency’. The reason of not filling their gap as they fear of the argumentation which may leads to bond breaking.

But Marquez created a situation where they try to express their emotion at the end of Urbino's life where they cannot get a second chance. When Fermina saw the fallen Urbino and at his last breath both has no words which were at the end of their tongue but they can convey only through emotion which has been understand. Before they create a problem to converse but not successful which is a silly issue of replacing soap but then did not need a issue or reason to speak.

After his death, Fermina suffers with stream of consciousness where at one point, she felt that the dead people has to take things and memories along with them, as they haunt the closest. Such is the marital love. Marquez portrays the marital love with different shades and conveys that the bonding in marital life which needs respect and trust to sustain their relationship.

Love Affairs:

Florentino Ariza had 622 affairs due to different reasons but few women are significant in his life. Among his affairs some are forced sex, some committed due to emergency love, some are searching for love, some are short span, some are night birds, affairs with concubines, etc,. Florentino never accept that he is a sensualist instead he justifies himself as they find solace and compassion in him. Marquez portrays the free life of Latin America through Florentino Ariza in this novel. The narrator also focuses the reason behind their weaknesses. The reason behind his affair with each woman has different reason and the women are focussed as unsatisfied in their relationship and search for the companionship. Marquez highlights the positivity rather than negativity in their relationship.

Florentino Ariza, who wants to be faithful and virgin to his lover, Fermina but for the first time, he was literally forced to make sex and lost his virginity in a boat where he was working with whom he done was never known. Later, widow Nazaret was sent by Florentino's mother, Transisto Ariza, with whom he makes love without his consent. His mother expects that the widow would relieve him from his fever of Fermina but instead she find solace in him as her husband dead a long time ago. Both were an unexpected incidents happened in his life which realizes him that women

are making love because of their sexual dissatisfaction. So, he made himself to satisfy according to their needs.

In case of Rosalba, whom he came across in his workplace he was attracted and admired her. There are some affairs where the married women crave for companionship like Ausencia Santander, a married and mother of three children. In this case, the marital life is different from companionship where they need a heart which can satisfy their sensual love. Leona Cassiani, companion in his work place with whom he even shared his secret love i.e., Fermina. He had never made love as he calls her as 'true woman in his life'. Some relations will not need physical love and never expects from other, made him to realize that all relations will not go to bed but withstands as a good companion in their lives.

Marquez present that women can also be free minded and accepts the fate of the life and live happily whatever they acquire. Sara Noriega, whom he met in a poetic festival and invites her to console her heart and with whom he maintained the longest and stable affair. She is a woman who never bothers about the men who did not come with proposal of marriage but relays on having men on bed '*with or without marriage, or God, or the law, life was not worth living without a man in her bed*' (). The man or woman who was abandon by their loves will never depress themselves but move on their life according to their wish. Marquez draws the two characters who were abandoned by their first loves have taken granted of their fate and move on their lives. In the life of Sara Noriega, there is a fear of her private life which should not to be public as she uses '*infant's pacifier*' during her emergency love. He calls his affair as '*clandestine adventure*' which sets his making love with secrecy. This reminds of Jeremiah's affair with a mulatto who also maintains secrecy as they respect the conventions of the society. Unlike Fermina, Sara is also same as Fermina in stubbornness but the thing varies is Sara lives for her own sake same as in relationship with whom she want to maintain though they are occasional lovers. Florentino calls her 'crazy lady' but she is the one from whom he cured from the disease of love and made immune to the love towards Fermina which his mother failed. The reason is she made him to immune and not to stop the life at that moment and not to suffer with stream of conscious. She gave Florentino her

definition of love and a path to lead the life. She never stops at one person as not to subject to men's treachery.

The affairs sometimes will lead to tragedy and pathetic which shows the intensity of the illegitimate affairs will pay back. Through Olimpia Zuleta, Marquez shows the betrayal of a wife to her husband will lead to tragedy. She presents a pigeon in a cage, which means that she is a pigeon who wants freedom to fly off from the conventions of the society. The solitary hunter at last got his bird, Olimpia, where he enjoyed his love. Through Olimpia, the narrator shows the weakness of Florentino who cannot face the public and fear of revelation of identity with whom she slept, as she was killed by her husband. He came out in to the public until he knew that she has not revealed his name. This incident sets an example for the value of conventions of the society they are bound and fear of punishment by the society, though the people are doing it secretly but they do not want be a offender in the society. The same in the case of Senorita, he makes a relationship with her in the office which shows the recklessness of Florentino who has caught red handed by his Uncle Leo XII. But he slips off from the place which shows that the condition of Florentino has slipped out of his hand. The people know about him but they left to his fate.

We can see Jeremiah de Saint Armour, Florentino Ariza and Dr. Juvenal Urbino are the people having status in the society who have illicit relationships but they cannot publicize it because they fear to the conventions of the society

Marquez portrays Florentino's character as 'he was immune not to love but only to women'. This proves that why he claims himself as 'virgin'. Through Sara Noriega gave the theory of divided love as "She said: "Spiritual love from the waist up and physical love from the waist down". This statement can be taken in to consideration which defines the love how we can look into. As love is not of sex but beyond the body we have to look into.

This paper mainly focuses on love and sex with different shades and the role of man in different situations where he has hurdles to face in order to acquire his love. The love and sex are not interlinked sometimes where love will ultimately leads to sex and sex did not need to have love. The love at different ages will changes its facets and sometimes it disguises as love has fade

away but in real at that situation it increases the bonding of individual. It is not about a triangular love story but a pure love is put to a test where as always its victory is inescapable. The question of acquiring the love is sometimes disguised as illicit but it is not essential for the lovers of what means they are employing. It also collides with the conventions of the society where they are not acquiring the love. Here, we remember of the universal saying i.e. everything is fair in love and war.

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